

Electronic prototype for signal modulation of luminance in operating photovoltaic modules

The present document aims to describe how to build an electronic board that can be connected within a PV string to modulate electroluminescence (EL) and photoluminescence (PL) signals while the PV module is in normal operation. The following files are attached for the construction of the electronic board:

- Schematic file: electronic blocks of the board
- Gerber file: for PCB construction
- BOM file: summary of components required
- Hex file: Code

The topology of the circuit and its connection within a PV string are shown below. Moreover, the supplementary table indicates which MOSFETs must be conducting to achieve three different states in the solar module, enabling the modulation of the electroluminescence or photoluminescence signal.

The board is based on two MOSFETs and two diodes. Each state means a different emission intensity regarding luminance signal:

- OC: maximum PL signal and zero EL signal
- MPP: almost null PL and EL signal
- CI: maximum PL signal and maximum EL signal

1. Communications

The electronics are based on six blocks, which can be seen in the schematic file: Power circuit, supply and microcontroller circuit, control circuit, transmission circuit, reception circuit, and anti-saturation coil. The transmission circuit, reception circuit, and anti-saturation coil are included in the design to enable power line communication through the DC cable of the string. However, these components are not explained in this document, as communication is carried out via the microcontroller's serial port. Therefore, if communication is done through the serial port, these components do not need to be included in the board.

The board includes two connectors: H1 for programming and H3 for communication via the serial port. An external module is required for communication, such as an HC-05/06 for Bluetooth or a USB-to-UART (TTL) module (e.g., FT232RL, CP2102, PL2303HX) for USB communication

2. Power supply

Note that the board does not require an external power supply or batteries, as it operates using the voltage from the solar module. It is important to highlight that the linear voltage regulator, which reduces the module voltage to 5V, is undersized. This may cause the board to shut down due to the regulator's thermal protection, especially when the module has a high voltage. Therefore, we recommend adding a heat sink to the integrated circuit, using two regulators in parallel, or selecting a regulator with a higher current supply capability.

3. Code

The hex file that must be loaded into the microcontroller (PIC16F1619) allows proper control of the board. Commands can be sent in ASCII format through its serial port. The implemented commands are:

- Use the command **"1\r\n"** to set the module to open circuit.
- Use the command **"2\r\n"** to set the module to normal operation (maximum power point).
- Use the command **"3\r\n"** to enable reverse current (current injection).
- Use the command **"4\r\n"** to generate a square wave (4 Hz) between OC and CI.
- Use the command **"5\r\n"** to generate a half-sine wave (4 Hz) between OC and CI. *
- Use the command **"6\r\n"** to generate a sine wave (4 Hz) between OC and CI. *

** Sine and half-sine modulation require additional hardware on the board. An LC filter must be implemented between the board and the tested module, with a cutoff frequency lower than the PWM frequency used in the MOSFETs (5 kHz). The modulation of half-sine and sine waves significantly increases MOSFET temperatures, so it is not recommended to maintain these types of modulation for more than 40 seconds.*

Once the state is set, the board sends back a message indicating the selected state.